

Vocational Education in China: Its History, Challenges and the Policies Development

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Abstract:

Vocational education plays an essential role in developing diverse human talents, passing on technical skills, and promoting employment, innovation, and entrepreneurship. As a critical part of the national education system and the development of human resources, vocational education in China plays a crucial role in the development of diverse talents, the transfer of technical skills, and the promotion of employment and entrepreneurship. This paper aims to explore the history, challenges, and the Policies Development for vocational education in China. It is found that vocational education in China has gone through a series of name changes before settling on its current nomenclature. Although vocational education is essential to complement general academic education to build a nation, it faces an uphill battle to gain the same status and recognition bestowed on general education. These challenges include curriculum design, poor linkages with industries, public perception, and other structural issues. This paper also discusses policy evolution of vocational education in China

Keywords: vocational education, technical and vocational education, challenges, Policies Development

1 Introduction:

has continued to implement new rules that are being tested in a bunch of areas to improve the exam-oriented school environment and accomplish the goal of quality education. It is committed to identifying the most effective education policies currently in place and promoting them on a large scale. Although each policy change is tiny in quantity, they occur frequently, such as the “double reduction” which reduces the burden of homework and off-campus instruction for students in compulsory education to build a high-quality education system in China, resulting in after-school extended hours services and secondary school triage.

In China, higher vocational education is part of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET). According to UNESCO's (2003) International Standard Classification of Education 1997, rather than leading directly to an advanced

research qualification such as a degree, higher vocational education is in the junior stage of post-secondary education. It provides programs focusing on specific skills and practical occupational for workforce preparation. In addition, public higher vocational education is the major component of higher vocational education. It includes several categories, such as adult colleges, independent vocational and technical colleges, regular junior colleges, independent four-year colleges, and vocational and technical colleges run by universities. While most institutions are designed as institutions with two to three-year programmes, higher vocational education programs last up to five years in some secondary vocational schools at the upper secondary level.

Since the reform and opening up in 1978, China's vocational education has undergone a process of significant development and transformation. It has produced many high-level technical and skilled talents, extensively promoting China's socialist market economy. The reform has also improved the overall cultural literacy of the public and enhanced the general happiness of the society (Guo, 2010).

2 The History of Education and Vocational Education in China:

Education is fundamental to the well-being of a nation and is the foundation for a strong country. The Chinese government has permanently attached great importance to education and has given priority to its development. It has established the world's most extensive education system, guaranteeing the rights of hundreds of millions of Chinese people to receive education and significantly improving the quality of the entire nation. At the end of 2020, China had 537,100 schools of all types and levels, increasing 7,000 or 1.33% from 2019. There were 289 million students in schools at all levels, up 6.7448 million or 2.39% since 2019. There were 17,929,700 full-time teachers, 609,400 more than in 2019, or an increase of 3.52%. The average length of education of the newly added labour force nationwide was 13.8%, 0.1 years higher than in 2019, and 53.5% of them received higher education, 2.6% higher than in 2019 (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2021).

The Qing Dynasty's reign of terror came to an end in 1911 with China's first civic revolt against feudalism, ushering in a new era in the development of vocational education. Huang Yampi, Cai Yuan Pei, Tao Xianzhi, and others founded the Chinese Vocational Education Society in 1917. They paved the way for China's education and industrial sectors to collaborate on vocational education. It was the first organization in modern China dedicated to the study, provision, and promotion of technical and vocational education. The organization assisted its members in expanding their knowledge and abilities in agriculture, industry, and commerce, ushering in a new era of technical and vocational education (Wu, X., & Ye, Y. 2018).

Located in northwest China and the upper reaches of the Yellow River, the Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region, abbreviated "Ning", covers a land area of 66,400 square kilo metres and consists of five prefectural-level cities, including Yinchuan, Shizuishan, Wuzhong, Guyuan, and Zhongwei, and 22 counties (cities and districts). Ningxia has a permanent population of 7,202,654 and is one of China's five ethnic autonomous regions. Among permanent residents, there are 1,248,938 people with university education (college education or above), 967,429 people with high school education (including technical secondary school education), and 2,140,403 people with junior high school education. The population with primary education is 1,880,672 (Statistics Bureau of the Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region, 2021). In 2020, Ningxia had 39 independent vocational schools, 12 higher vocational schools, 27 secondary vocational schools, 31 public schools, and six private schools. These schools had 132,000 students, of whom 57,000 were in higher vocational schools and 75,000 in secondary vocational schools, including 7,000 in technical schools (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2021).

Vocational education has a historical and dynamic concept endowed with new meanings with time development (Cong & Wang, 2012). In modern China, the idea

of vocational education has resulted in long-standing and numerous debates. In 1904, the term vocational education first appeared in Yao Wendong, the general office of Shanxi Agriculture and Forestry School; in his article, he opined that on the principles of education, one was General Education, and the other was vocational education, with the latter being more relevant to the people. Although the concept varied, they were complementary and not opposite. Before this, vocational education was also known as *Practical Education, Agriculture, Industry and Business, Arts, and Special Schools in China*. Collectively, they were referred to as industrial education. In 1917, Huang Yanpei, a famous educator in modern China, founded the Chinese Vocational Education Association in Shanghai, officially changing the name of Industrial Education to Vocational Education. Since then, vocational education has become a familiar name accepted by most people in education (Zhang & Sheese, 2017). In 1949, on the eve of the founding of the People's Republic of China, Zhu De, Li Lisan and Huang Yanpei suggested that the development of vocational education should be included in the Common Program of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference, but this attracted fierce opposition from dogmatists. The Common Program adopted by the political party only included technical education in addition to formal education. Technical education has replaced vocational education.

To begin with, many specially trained secondary schools and highly qualified schools were founded in the 1950s to meet the demands of economic growth. During the first national education conference after the establishment of the People's Republic of China, the customary condition of a gap between general education and TVE was raised. The State Council released the Decision on Improving Secondary Technical and Vocational Education in 1954 to reform and develop secondary vocational education, and the Ministry of Education issued the Secondary Special Schools Regulation in the meantime. As a result, China's TVE system has become more focused on secondary vocational and technical schools. Secondary technical and vocational education met the needs of economic development to a large extent. By 1957, there were 844,833 students enrolled in secondary vocational and technical institutions, accounting for 48.3% of total students (Wu, X. P., & Ye, Y. Q. 2018). Between 1958 and 1976, China's technical and vocational education grew rapidly, with many new vocational schools opening and numerous students enrolling.

3- Policies Development

Economic and societal changes are posing severe challenges to the growth of vocational education in China (Li, Y. P., & Lumby, J. (2005). Decades of policy reform have resulted in progress, but there are serious doubts about its sufficiency remain.

At the 97th meeting of the Government Affairs Council on the 10th of August in 1951, Zhou Enlai, the Chinese Premier, stated that the previous Chinese educational system was modelled after that of Japan and afterwards

the United States. Despite certain changes, it was still classified as a capitalist educational system. The Government Council issued the Decision on Reforming the Length of Schooling System on the 1st of October in 1951, stating that China's original educational system has many flaws, the most serious of which is the cadre school for workers and farmers, as well as various cram schools and training classes, which have no due status in the school system(Sun, C. X. 2018)

Deng Xiaoping's southern tour speech and the 14th National Congress of the Communist Party of China both proposed the establishment of a socialist market economic system at the beginning of 1992. Since Deng Xiaoping's open-door policy was released in the late 1970s, Chinese vocational education has demonstrated enormous energy in its development (Lumby, J., & Ping, L. Y. 1998). The Chinese government has published and implemented a succession of vocational education policies during the last two decades to meet the prerequisites for its economic transition to what is allegedly a socialist market economy. Colleges and universities were extended from 1999 to 2006. Vocational schools are unable to develop due to a lack of pupils. Resources must be allocated at the national level to address the educational gap, instead of abandoning vocational education.

The recent policy has not made many significant changes. Previously, there was no distinction between ordinary and vocational high schools in terms of enrolment. The "Decision on Accelerating the Development of Modern Vocational Education" was published by the State Council in June 2014, and it was widely adopted to accelerate the development of modern professional education. It outlined the overarching philosophy, core concepts, goals, tasks, tactics, and measures for advancing contemporary vocational education in the coming years. Secondly, "Advancing the Growth of a Modern Vocational Education System," specifies that "professional higher vocational colleges should work closely with industry, universities, and research institutes to cultivate technical and technical individuals serving regional development. Higher vocational education should include the school's current circumstances as well as a variety of successful ways, which strives to create a new professional vocational education centring on "(Gao, Z., & Yu, T. 2020)talents as the centre, employers' satisfaction as the standard" After 2021, all areas will require a balanced proportion of regular and vocational high schools, with vocational education enrolling a growing proportion of pupils.

4- Challenges Facing Vocational Education in China:

China has the most extensive vocational education globally. It has grown by leaps and bounds in a relatively short period, providing opportunities for millions of students from low-income families and skills training to boost the economy. However, vocational education in China faces various challenges. According to

Steward (2015), these challenges could be viewed and summarized from curriculum design, industry connections, status, and structures. The following sections summarize these challenges:

a. Vocational education curriculum lacks breadth

Many of the vocational education programmes in China focus mainly on the entry-level skills needed for students to secure their first job instead of providing a more profound and broader skillset required for career advancement. This phenomenon has its roots in the human resource planning model that had set the foundation for schools' development in China (Wu & Ye, 2018). Although there have been efforts to broaden vocational education curricula, the skills training provided is not high enough to meet the demand of the changing economic landscape to allow the individual to advance economically. Apart from that, curriculum development is not designed in partnership with leading companies with cutting edge technology nor advancing the economy in mind. There was little focus on entrepreneurship and innovation, two components gaining greater traction in the world economy.

b. The Low Quality of the Academic Study:

The key factors include a lack of societal investment, a high level of government participation, and a lack of academic flexibility. Furthermore, children are classified into several school categories based on their entrance exam scores, with vocational schools being treated as second-class institutions. There is a scarcity of qualified teachers and instructors in vocational institutions (Sun, L.2010).

c. A Low Public Perception

A cultural issue exists in addition to the fragile linkages to industry. The Chinese concept that “those who conduct mental labour may rule those who perform manual labour” traces back to Confucius' Analects and has shaped how the Chinese view knowledge and education (Stewart, V.,2015). These differences between academic and practical education exist in other countries, but they are more pronounced in China. As a result, the public regards vocational education as low status.

d. Less Required Skills to Improve Students' Competence

This is due in part to the manpower planning paradigm that guided the growth of several of the schools (Stewart, V.,2015)However, as the lifespan of work skills shortens and China's economy shifts, VET will need to include more general education to prepare people to be more adaptable and capable of learning new skills.

CONCLUSION

As a type of education closely related to economic and social development, vocational education is an important channel to develop technical talents to build a nation. This paper has reviewed the brief history of Chinese vocational education clarified its roles and challenges facing vocational education in China. Even if they believe it is beneficial to master a talent, parents and kids will avoid becoming technically adept for fear of not being recognized in today's culture, which expects high qualifications. As a result, the government should adopt a set of measures to entice parents and children to pursue vocational education. The government should, for example, provide employment incentives to competent workers. Schools are recommended to provide students with structured and appropriately compensated internships. During the application process, vocational institutions can also hold information sessions at schools. As a result, more funding will be available for vocational education, and there will be a promising future in this field.

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